

Evolution of Feminist Discourse in Canadian Literature: From Expressive Realism to Empowering Narratives

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Abstract:

The complicated and dynamic narrative of feminism in Canadian literature reflects the country's greater social and cultural changes. Before the 1980s, expressive realism, a literary strategy that sought to portray reality in a vivid and emotional way, was the main characteristic of English-Canadian feminist writing. But literary critics and academics of the era frequently emphasised portraying women as passive objects of observation rather than active contributors to the formation of knowledge and discourse. This strategy did not address representation, gender, or language issues theoretically. In this setting, women were frequently portrayed as subjects of study rather than knowledge makers, which maintained their marginalised position. Women writers from England-Canada were encouraged to experiment with their writing techniques in order to subvert the country's predominate expressive realist discourse. By deviating from accepted norms, these authors aimed to investigate topics and viewpoints that had previously been disregarded or repressed. This article looks into Canadian narratives, especially women's contributions to literature.

Keywords: Canadian narrative, feminism, realism, women's contributions, intellectual thinking, historical aspects etc.

Introduction:

It is crucial to remember that up until recently, women's contributions to literature and intellectual thinking were routinely neglected or marginalised. Because women's lives and opinions were not historically recorded, it was believed that they did not write or engage in significant intellectual pursuits. Women's history was frequently considered as a subset of social history, distinct from more general intellectual or cultural history, which made the situation worse. Methodological issues have presented a barrier to academics and researchers interested in women's history. They needed to figure out how to hear the voices and understand the experiences of women who were frequently shut out of formal education, illiterate, and restricted to private spaces. In order to shed light on the contributions that women made to society, culture, and intellectual thinking, this project attempted to shine light on the experiences of women who were mostly absent from the historical record. The representation and victimisation of women in Canadian history were significantly altered by Canadian

feminists. Their work attempted to challenge the dominant narratives that had consigned women to the background by highlighting the experiences, views, and accomplishments of women. These feminists contributed to a more complete and accurate understanding of Canadian history and literature by highlighting the value of women's perspectives and stories. As the feminist movement gained momentum, it prompted a re-evaluation of the canons of literature and history and increased understanding of the diversity of voices and experiences in Canadian literature. A more broad and nuanced approach to understanding literature, history, and culture in Canada was made possible by this revisiting of the past.

Without a doubt, Canadian literature is rich and varied, covering a vast range of genres and themes that have been inspired by numerous elements, such as geography, history, and the particular Canadian experience. Early Canadian literary narratives were significantly shaped by the colonial period, and authors like Susanna Moodie and Catherine Parr Traill have had a lasting influence on the field. Sisters from England who came to Canada in the 1830s, Susanna Moodie and Catherine Parr Traill, wrote about their adventures as explorers in the Canadian wilderness. Their writings, like Parr Traill's *The Backwoods of Canada* (1836) and Moodie's *Roughing It in the Bush* (1852), offered first-person tales of living in the difficult and untamable Canadian environment. These stories emphasised the hardships, strategies for surviving, and fortitude needed to prosper in the new environment. Their writings included thoughts on how people interact with the natural world, a major theme in early Canadian literature, in addition to tales of their own experiences. The harsh Canadian environment, with its enormous forests and erratic weather, took on a key role in their tales. Throughout Canadian literature, the concepts of survival and the interaction between humans and nature persisted.

It is interesting to note that these themes appeared in later works by well-known Canadian authors like Margaret Atwood. Atwood examined the idea of survival as a recurrent subject in Canadian literature in her book *Survival: A Thematic Guide to Canadian Literature* (1972). She looked at how Canadian authors, like Moodie and Parr Traill before them, struggled with survival—both literally and figuratively—as they dealt with the difficulties of a harsh environment and defended their cultural identity against outside influences. The way later generations of Canadian writers approached issues of survival, adaptation, and the complexity of the country's geography is a good indication of Moodie and Parr Traill's influence. Their

contributions provided the groundwork for the literary study of distinctly Canadian experiences, and they still serve as an inspiration for authors today.

Canadian poetry underwent a tremendous transition in the 1960s and 1970s, establishing itself as a vibrant and dynamic literary form. Poets like Margaret Atwood, Margaret Avison, Phyllis Webb, and Gwendolyn MacEwen, noted for their avant-garde and experimental approaches to poetry, became important players during this time. By embracing postmodernist methods, these poets gave Canadian verse a fresh new energy. Their poetry covered a wide range of subjects, reflecting the changing social and cultural climate of the time. Within their lyrics, political issues, analyses of popular culture, feminism, discussions of environment, and inquiries into scientific humanism all found a home. Particularly notable among the prolific poets was Margaret Atwood, who was also a renowned novelist and literary critic.

Other notable Canadian writers rose to prominence during the 20th century as well. Among the eminent authors who significantly influenced Canadian writing were Margaret Laurence, Gabrielle Roy, and Carol Shields. Furthermore, Alice Munro has the distinction of being regarded as one of the best current short story authors in the English language thanks to her mastery of the short story genre. Collectively, they helped Canadian literature gain international recognition by showcasing its distinctive voices, viewpoints, and narratives. It is important to remember, though, that the Canadian literary scene wasn't always as active. Few works with true literary worth were published in Canada during the post-war decades. The difficulty Canadian writing had in standing out from bigger international literary currents and creating its own unique voice is highlighted by this scarcity. The rise of the writers previously listed was a watershed event that contributed to making Canadian literature a major player on the world literary scene.

Victimization in Writing:

The way victimisation and power dynamics are portrayed in fiction has been greatly influenced by Canadian women writers. They have offered nuanced and complex representations of women's power and strength throughout their works. These representations cover a wide range of images that reflect both traditional and modern views on the agency and impact of women. Tradition-based representations of women's power are among the many that

Canadian women writers have examined. These include more complicated ideas like witchcraft and the maternal role as well as demonstrations of power through symbols like clothing and hairstyles. These authors also look at how women have historically taken on tasks that society typically assigns to men, such as using weapons like knives and guns and succeeding in fields that have historically been dominated by men. The investigation of women's sexual liberation and their usage of male terminology push the boundaries of preconceived concepts of authority.

New and innovative depictions of women's power have also been made by contemporary women writers. Advocating for individual freedom of choice, embracing androgyny, and expressing and processing strong emotions are a few examples. The capacity to convey one's distinct vision, frequently through artistic expression, has developed into a crucial means of making one's power known. Women writers have been integral to the growth of Canadian literature from the beginning and are frequently undervalued for their contributions. Women's diaries and memoirs from the early periods of settlement show that they were actively involved not just in home domains but also in family management and helping to meet the needs of the land. This historical event shows that women weren't just restricted to parlours and drawing rooms. This heritage of active participation is still there today, with many women writers succeeding not only in literature but also in many other professions. Because they authentically convey tradition and explore the search for reality, the works of Canadian women authors are appealing. Their stories provided insight into the oppression that both individuals and groups experienced, bringing up these concerns for debate and analysis. In this sense, Canadian women writers have paved the way for writing that challenges power dynamics, celebrates resiliency, and elevates the voices of people who are frequently silenced or ignored.

Feminism by Reading:

The study of women's experiences and voices in literature is where feminism first emerged. *Of Woman Born* by Adrienne Rich is a key piece of feminist literature that is intricately woven into the very fabric of feminism. Women now have the space to think beyond their existing circumstances thanks to literature and the intellectual world. Early feminism raised questions about the future of the traditional family unit. The family has had tremendous power throughout history and is still a powerful force in modern society, so this worry was not unwarranted. Although there have been a few pieces on women's issues included since 1940,

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the biggest addition was in 1979. The education of young girls from different social backgrounds is sometimes given only passing consideration in even current feminist analyses of ideology.

It is interesting to note that intellectual historians have mostly focused on researching Canada's conservative ideological characteristics. A constrained examination of the feminist movement and its contributions is the outcome of this perspective. Early English-Canadian feminists pursued political compromise, respectability, and the opportunity to vote rather than advocating for complete liberation. It is crucial to remember that these early feminists had a different viewpoint from radical nationalism. Although some authors, including Micheline Johnson, Yolande Pinard, and Jennifer Stoddart, have asserted that feminism and nationalism are incompatible, it is important to note that this is not a universally held opinion. The interaction between feminism and nationalism is complicated and varies based on the situation and the individual's personal views. In Canada, there is a complex web of connections between feminism, literature, ideology, and nationalism. The study of these topics contributes to a better understanding of the historical and social forces that have influenced the women's movement and its interactions with other sociopolitical currents.

Feminists were searching for historical examples that supported their more extreme beliefs in the 1970s. But the agendas of intellectual historians may diverge from the specific objectives of the feminist movement. While historians must admit that both feminists and conventional authorities perceived women as engaging in similar activities, feminists may believe that historical narratives were shaped to fit with prevailing orthodoxies. These included self-help, moral growth, wifely and household obligations, as well as involvement in charitable and religious activities. Feminists should understand that, while suffrage was one aspect of a variety of initiatives that spurred feminist efforts in the early 20th century, it was only one part of the difficult battle for women's suffrage in Quebec against conservative and ecclesiastical resistance.

The idea of "separate spheres" can irritate historians who are attempting to identify the intellectual and ideological foundations of the discrimination and oppression experienced by women. Males and women should naturally belong in various social spheres, with males in the public sphere and women in the domestic sphere, according to the idea of separate spheres. This ideology supported gender-based disparities and was frequently used to defend women's

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exclusion from public life. In light of this, historians' dissatisfaction as they look into how certain beliefs persist is reasonable. The idea of "separate spheres" has been ingrained in historical accounts and has influenced society conventions. Historians can help us understand the causes of gender inequality and the challenging fight for women's rights by closely examining the historical roots of women's oppression and exclusion. Overall, this text emphasises the conflict between the historical study of gender roles and the developing feminist viewpoints that want to question and topple established customs and hierarchies of power.

Intellectual History:

Intellectual historians in Canada have frequently focused their research on nationalism, and their work started to garner attention during the Quiet Revolution. Their research has centred on how the country is portrayed. These historians have unintentionally neglected women's existence and accomplishments due to their focus on nationalism. Women are frequently portrayed as flimsy reflections of what these historians might have wished them to be when they are mentioned. Feminism and nationalism's meeting point could lead to a novel method of intellectual history. Researchers could dive into the genesis and transmission of ideas by examining the roles that women played in constructing ideology, potentially giving fresh light on how intellectual thought is formed. The danger of "presentism," which entails putting contemporary ideals and viewpoints onto historical contexts, is another typical pitfalls in existing feminist studies that this strategy may help to avoid. To ensure a more accurate understanding of past ideologies, it is imperative to balance this risk.

Notably, intellectual history has typically been followed without giving careful account to the contributions that women made to the development of the ideas of significant male thinkers. The influence of women on the intellectual landscape has frequently been underappreciated because males have made up the bulk of intellectual historians. In conclusion, historians can uncover hitherto unrecognised aspects of historical ideologies and the creation of ideas by including both feminism and nationalism into the study of intellectual history. A more nuanced and inclusive understanding of the intricate web of thought and ideology throughout history may be achieved by addressing the exclusion of women's contributions and points of view from traditional intellectual history.

The broader feminist movement that was taking place in Western cultures throughout the 1970s had a considerable influence on the rebirth of interest in women's history, a development that was also clearly noticeable in Canada. Intellectual historians should take particular note of the fact that this feminist movement offered a theoretical framework that had a profound impact on women's history. The ideals of patriarchy and the relationships between genders served as the driving forces behind the feminist movement and later shaped the narrative of women's history. Both ideas posed a challenge to the dominant historical narrative, which frequently focused on class conflict and the dominance of one class over another. Instead, they highlighted how crucial gender dynamics were in determining the course of history. These connections were seen as significant historical factors, whether they were purely dominated by male dominance (patriarchy) or had more complex interactions involving different facets of society, including family, religion, politics, the economy, and ideas.

According to this viewpoint, the status accorded to women at any particular time can be used to judge how far a society has come. In addition to economic, demographic, and political issues, the predominate views and representations of women in that society also had an impact on this status. As a result, the advancement of women's standing and the acknowledgment of their historical agency were entwined with the greater backdrop of societal advancement. Women's history is a rich and uncharted region for intellectual historians looking for fresh areas to explore. Historians can learn more about the intricate interaction of ideas, cultural norms, and historical changes that have impacted relationships between men and women across time by examining the theoretical foundations of gender dynamics. In short, intellectual historians now have a fascinating opportunity to delve into a hitherto uncharted area of human history thanks to the feminist movement's influence on women's history and the ensuing change in viewpoint regarding the importance of gender relations in historical narratives. Understanding historical processes and cultural change more thoroughly requires acknowledging the agency, viewpoints, and contributions of women.

Historians of Feminism:

Intellectual historians might study the early 20th century feminist movements, particularly those that were prevalent in Western countries like Canada. This investigation might help historians comprehend the feminism's fall in the 1920s by highlighting the intellectual contributions made by women to the movement. This area of research may also

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interact with feminist theorists who see the entire ideological superstructure as a further manifestation of patriarchy that upholds the inferior status of women. Studying these movements could also shed light on the processes through which ideas are passed down through the generations. Intellectual historians need to focus on the demise of feminism in the 1920s. Investigating this trend may aid women's history scholars in explaining the circumstances that led to the waning of the feminist movement at that time. This investigation may shed light on the intricate interactions between societal, political, and intellectual advancements that shaped the course of feminist movements.

The role women played in supplying intellectual sustenance for the broader feminist ideology is another significant component that intellectual historians should investigate. Historians can gain a wealth of knowledge about the philosophical underpinnings of feminism and the manner in which women interacted with and developed its ideas by examining the writings, speeches, and intellectual contributions of women within these movements. The idea that entire intellectual systems could be viewed as continuations of patriarchy, maintaining women's subordination, is a source of debate. This viewpoint calls on intellectual historians to critically analyse feminist theory. While some feminist theorists suggest that ingrained conceptions support patriarchy, others assert that these systems may be overturned by changing these ideals. Intellectual historians have the chance to analyse and add to this discussion by participating in it. A historical analysis of the topic of idea transmission between generations would also be very beneficial. Feminist historians have identified the clergy, educational systems, and families as agents of transmission. It is interesting to note that modern feminists frequently view some of these agents as conservative and constrictive influences, especially the clergy and the family. This irony highlights the intricate interaction of historical elements that affects how people view and interact with these organisations.

In the end, modern feminists of the 1970s acknowledged that one of their most important battles involved overcoming deeply ingrained stereotypes and attitudes about women, particularly those that are instilled from a young age. Investigating these facets can help us gain a thorough grasp of the connections between concepts, assumptions, and attitudes as well as broader cultural shifts and intellectual advancements.

Conclusion:

In fact, the writings of female authors like Susan Howe and male avant-garde writers from movements like Tish and Open Letter have linkages with Canadian feminist writing. These connections highlight how feminist literature has several facets and engages with a variety of literary influences and strategies. Canadian feminist authors have been influenced by the Tish group, a Vancouver-based group of avant-garde poets, and Open Letter, a literary journal that published avant-garde and experimental work. Feminist writers were drawn to their experimental and cutting-edge work because it provided fresh viewpoints and literary techniques that they could use to communicate their own distinctive stories and struggles. Canadian feminist novelists have also benefited greatly from the inspiration of authors like Susan Howe. Howe's writing frequently explores language, history, and the nuances of identity; these are topics that are central to feminist literature. Canadian feminist writers have discovered a way to investigate and articulate their own thoughts and experiences in novel and thought-provoking ways by relying on Howe's writings and methods. The dynamic character of feminist literature, which aims to engage with a diverse variety of voices and viewpoints to form a more inclusive and nuanced discourse, is shown by this merging of influences. The complexity and diversity of the feminist literary scene in Canada is illustrated by the appropriation of concepts and methods from both male avant-garde writers and female literary pioneers like Susan Howe.

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